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THE EFFECTIVENESS OF COMPUTER AIDED INSTRUCTION (CAI) AS A SUPPLEMENTARY TOOL FOR TEACHERS IN CLASSROOM TEACHING

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Abstract

Computer is the dynamic teaching machine, versatile in nature. The storage, retrieval and transfer facilities available in computer can best be utilised for educational purposes. The speed, accuracy and personalised approach is useful for teaching students requiring varied kinds of inputs. The multimedia approach by computer can be made use in teaching different content areas in schools. The present study is experimental in nature and two groups having 30 students in each were taught with two different modes. The study tries to compare the effects of teaching by both the methods (namely conventional method of teaching and CAI package) and suggest few suggestions for further research. It is observed that the teachers' role is continuously changing from information disseminator to guide, software developer, and manager of hardware etc. The computers help teacher in access of resources and logical arrangements of classroom presentation.

Introduction

"Once children learn how to learn, nothing is going to narrow their mind. The essence of teaching is to make learning contagious, to have one idea spark another."

-Marva Collins

This quote not only deems fit for disabled children but suits more with normal children studying in the normal school. Teachers have the creative role to spark the ideas. The Kothari Commission (1964-66) laid emphasis on school education and gave highest importance to classroom transactions. It said, "The destiny of India is now being shaped in her classrooms". But, the argument here is that mere congregation of children in a classroom does not guarantee that education is imparted. Supply of various teaching aids for learning may spark ideas and help child to learn based on their background and knowledge. But, at this point of time the constructivists may also agree that teacher's role cannot be undermined in shaping students in the classroom. The resourcefulness of teachers is of utmost importance while teaching students in the classroom. Teacher has to make use of his/her knowledge, ability and teaching aids like computers in a useful way.

The computers have revolutionised various aspects of our life and also affected our thought processes. The computers have great role to play in education too. The capacity of computers

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like storage, retrieval, dissemination of data, make it more versatile tool for teaching in schools. However, the responsibility of judicious use of computers rests with senior academic workers like teachers. Teachers can teach the students various aspects of education like school content (general knowledge, current affairs) through operations of computers. The teacher's work also involves planning of the lesson, imparting in the classroom, recording the progress of learners and giving feedback. Hence, the teachers have to play a multifaceted role during the use of computers like content expert, media expert, technician and guide children in identifying and learning proper content from such system. The use of computer in education is being made by various means like CAI, CML, CBT etc.

Computer Assisted Instruction (CAI), is a programme of instructional material presented by means of a computer or computer system. The online encyclopaedia Britannica writes, "The use of computers for teaching helps in presentation of content in a structured, systematic manner. The learner can proceed at his own speed and gain mastery over learning. His progress can be recorded. The CAI can be utilised better in a situation, when there is lack of teachers or experts in particular area of teaching. Hence, it is an urgent need to know the use CAI in teaching.

Objectives

1. To prepare the CAI package in science subject for 10th standard.
2. To impart the lesson through CAI package and conventional method.
3. To compare the effectiveness of teaching between CAI mode and conventional method.

Hypotheses

1. There is no significant difference between the achievement scores of control group and experimental group for pre-test-1 of the unit solar energy-1.
2. There is no significant difference between the achievement scores of control group and experimental group for post-test-1 of the unit solar energy-1.
3. There is no significant difference between the achievement scores of control group and experimental group for pre-test-2 of the unit solar energy-2.
4. There is no significant difference between the achievement scores of control group and experimental group for post-test-2 of the unit solar energy-2.

Review of Related Literature

The literature available from encyclopaedia, reference books, journals, surveys of educational researches, internet and other research sources were referred for in-depth knowledge about the intended problem.

Basturk (2005) findings suggest participants' learning capacity of the introductory statistics could be improved successfully when CAI is used as a supplement to regular lecture in teaching introductory statistics course. Tabassum (2004) revealed that the students taught through computer-assisted instruction as supplementary strategy performed significantly better

The students with high achievement level showed better results than those with low achievement level when taught through computer-assisted instruction. The computer-assisted instruction was found equally effective for both male and female students.

The study of Wade (2001) indicated that computer assisted instruction was an effective method of delivering information literacy skills instruction. Students were able to select an appropriate database for their topic and navigate through, select, and print information that supported their focus questions with minimal involvement on the part of the teacher. The tutorial/practice model proved to be effective. This model more thoroughly integrated information literacy skills into the curriculum and solved the logistical problems of media specialists teaching all students.

Methodology of Study

The present study is an experimental design. The purposive random sampling method was adopted for finalising sample. Before finalising the sample, the investigators administered SPM test on the whole class. The students whose scores on this test were falling under average category were selected; each group consisted of 30 students and was randomly assigned to experimental and controlled group respectively. The methods of teaching namely conventional method and CAI package, is the independent variable whereas academic achievement of the students was the dependent variable. Intelligence of students was the control variable.

The following tools were used in the study:

1. SPM test: The Standard Progressive Matrices test developed by Raven was administered on the students to know their intelligence.
2. Science text book: The tenth standard science text book of Karnataka was selected as the basis for the content. Solar energy unit was identified from the text book.
3. CAI Package: The computer aided instruction package was prepared by using two methods namely tutorial and drill and practice.
4. Achievement test: An achievement test was prepared for testing the students' performance before and after the experimental treatment.

Treatments: The present study consisted of two groups under study. The details of the group are briefed below:

Control Group: In this group the teacher was asked to teach the unit in usual manner using minimum teaching aids as done in case of regular classes. This mode of teaching mainly relied upon 'teaching by chalk and talk method, utilising textbooks as supplementary aids. The students activities were curtailed, their emotions, creative thinking were also controlled. This method allowed very less participation of the students, less use of teaching aids and

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there was no scope for students to react. The unit selected for this type of teaching were same as that of the experimental group.

Experimental Group: In this method the investigator designed CAI package on selected unit of 10th standard of science subject, which was same as that of previous programme. The teachers monitored students progress, clarified their doubts regarding content and package. Teacher also arranged pre and post instructional activities. Based on the anticipated needs of programme implementation, teachers were given training on conduct of activities, use of apparatus like computer and package content etc. The students were given freedom for learning at their own pace and freedom for asking doubts during learning.

Development of CAI Package

The development of CAI package is a long process and is an important aspect of present research. Hence, the investigator gave due importance for preparation of CAI packages. The stages involved in the development and standardisation of package are given in a flow chart in figure 1.

The programme planning was the first stage, where in the investigator decided about the content, presentation format, style of teaching, physical and financial requirements etc. This was carried forward to design of a CAI programme based on requirements of the stakeholders. The CAI has four style of presentation and the investigator restricted to the use of tutorial and drill & practice modes of teaching. The investigators then referred the material and planned outline of script and wrote the academic script of CAI programme. This was followed by consultations with software experts, who helped in finalisation of CAI script based on media requirements. The programmers or software experts were then asked to prepare CAI packages. At this stage the content and context specific pictures, animations, questions and feedbacks were integrated properly. Care was taken that the objectives of the programme remained prime concern. The media and content experts reviewed the programmes, edited and incorporated important aspects at appropriate places. The programme thus developed, were subjected to try-out in schools. The programmes were tested for their effectiveness with regard to software, type or format of CAI and planning aspects. The error free programmes were sent for final implementation in the schools. Based on detection of defects the programmes were sent for correction at appropriate stages as shown in the flow chart. The particulars of the software so developed are given in subsequent section.

Details of Software

Name: Computer Aided Instruction, Subject: Science, Class: 10th standard, Level: Secondary School, Hardware requirement: Computer, Monitor (VDU): Monitor of the Computer, User Interface: Keyboard and Mouse and Special Features: user friendly package.

Fig. 1 showing CAI programme preparation

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Validity of the Programme

The content selected for the programme was based on the objectives set for the programme. All the intended points were covered and properly presented in the programme. This shows that the content is valid. The programme content was based on the existing syllabus of SSLC prevailing in Karnataka. This was appropriate for present day needs. Hence it is concurrent. The programme was constructed based on learning theories. Interactivity was also built into it. Hence, it had construct validity. The CAI programme was a representative of individualised instruction. Hence, it had face validity. t- test was used to analyse data.

Data Analysis and Interpretation

H1: There is no significant difference between the scores of control group and experimental group for pre-test 1 of solar energy 1.

To test this hypothesis the investigators subjected data obtained to 't' test and the results are given the Table 1.

Table 1: t-value between control group and experimental group for pre-test

Group	N	df	Mean	SD	SE	t-value
Control	30	29	4.1	1.02	0.30	0.22
Exptl	30	29	4.16	1.28		

*not significant

From Table 1, it is inferred that the calculated value of 't' is 0.22 and the table value of 't' at 0.01 level of significance is 2.75. The table value of 't' is greater than the calculated value. Therefore, the null hypothesis H1 is accepted. Hence, it is concluded that there is no significant difference between the means of control group and experimental group for pre test score for the unit solar energy 1.

H2: There is no significant difference between the scores of control group and experimental group for post-test 1 of solar energy 1.

To test this hypothesis the investigators subjected data obtained to 't' test and the results are given in the table 2.

Table 2: t-value between control group and experimental group for post-test 1

Group	N	df	Mean	SD	SE	t-value
Control	30	29	7.96	0.85	0.48	31.45
Exptl	30	29	23.16	2.50		

*significant

From Table 2, it is inferred that the calculated value of 't' is 31.45 and the table value of 't' at 0.01 level of significance is 2.75. The table value of 't' is less than the calculated value. Therefore, the null hypothesis H2 is rejected. Hence, it indicates that there is significant difference between the means of control group and experimental group on post test score on solar energy1. After observing the means of both the group it can be drawn that the mean score is in favour of experimental. That is after treatment the achievement of experimental group is better than control group.

H3: There is no significant difference between the scores of control group and experimental group for pre-test 2 of solar energy 2.

To test this hypothesis the investigators subjected data obtained to 't' test and the results are given in the table 3.

Table 3: t-value between control group and experimental group for pre-test 2

Group	N	df	Mean	SD	SE	t-value
Control	30	29	3.93	0.82	0.24	1.21
Exptl	30	29	4.23	1.07		

*not significant

From table 3, it is inferred that the calculated value of 't' is 1.21 and the table value of 't' at 0.01 level of significance is 2.75. The table value of 't' is greater than the calculated value. Therefore, the null hypothesis H3 is accepted. Hence, it indicates that there is no significant difference between the means of control group and experimental group.

H4: There is no significant difference between the scores of control group and experimental group for pos- test 2 of solar energy 2.

To test this hypothesis the investigators subjected data obtained to 't' test and the results are given in the table 4.

Table 4: t-value between control and experimental group for post-test 2 in the unit solar energy 2

Group	N	df	Mean	SD	SE	t-value
Control	30	29	10.93	1.04	0.28	33.49
Exptl	30	29	20.33	1.12		

*significant

The table 4 indicates that the calculated value of 't' is 33.49 and the table value at 0.01 level of significance is 2.75. The table value of 't' is less than the calculated value. Therefore, the

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null hypothesis H₄ is rejected. Hence, there is significant difference between means of control and experimental group for post test 2 of Solar energy 2. Looking at the means it can be inferred that the mean score is in favour of experimental group. That means after treatment the achievement of experimental group is better than control group.

Findings

1. The students taught by conventional and CAI methods achieved equal scores before getting the treatment for the unit solar energy-1.
2. The students taught by the CAI package achieved better than the students taught by conventional method for the unit solar energy-1.
3. The students taught by conventional and CAI methods achieved equal scores before getting the treatment for the unit solar energy-2.
4. The students taught by the CAI package achieved better than the students taught by conventional method for the unit solar energy-2.

Suggestion for Further Research

The study should be extended both horizontally and vertically to different geographical locations, levels of teaching and subject areas. Comparative studies must be made among different areas listed above. There are many such areas, which can be studied for their effectiveness and creative and resourceful investigators are to think further on this area and strengthen use of technology in education.

Conclusion

There are many studies going on in the field of education and use of computer need to be studied more rigorously as computers are useful in different fields of life including education. Lack of access to computers, poor software and faculty members who are inadequately prepared to use computers effectively are reasons for failure of use of computers. But, at the same time the positive aspects of use of computers are the dramatic advances in capabilities, decreased costs, extensive familiarisation programme and widespread availability of computers. In this scenario teachers can access information through computers and use it for presentation of content to the classroom. There are various commercially available educational resources, which could be used for teaching. The teachers' role changes while making the use of these packages. It is based on the requirement of students that the teacher provides the content. The innovativeness, colourfulness, preparation format and individualised pattern of teaching help the learner better. The teacher can make use of simple packages like word, excel, power point, flash for teaching their content areas. The present study has demonstrated that the computer technology can be effectively used for teaching in the classroom.

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